

In this scheme the short-lived intermediates between rhodopsin and MII have been omitted. The scheme is a modification of the linear model given by Baumann (1972) for the kinetics of the photoproducts following substantial bleaches of the rhodopsin present in the living, isolated frog retina. However, though first-order kinetics are assumed, the situation may well be more complicated.

The modifications were found necessary in order to account for the results from measurements after bleaching only small (down to a few per cent) fractions of rhodopsin. The main modification as compared to Baumann's model is the assumption of two pathways for the decay of metarhodopsin III (MIII), one to bound retinal and one to free retinal. Thus the decay of MIII can be described by the overall rate constant $k_3 = k_{30} + \bar{k}_4$. For descriptions of the methods and the mode of analysis Donner & Hemilä (1974) should be consulted. They found that the values of the rate constants are increased when the fraction of rhodopsin bleached is below 20% of the total. At +14° and pH 7.5 of the perfusing Ringer's solution the following values for the rate constants were typical (in units 10^{-3} s^{-1}):

Bleach %	k_1	k_2	k_3	\bar{k}_4
20	6	4	1.1	0.9
6	9	18	1.5	1.1
3	17	40	3	1.1

The strong increase of k_2 gives the result that very little MIII is produced after a weak bleach, a typical situation under normal conditions of seeing.

Preliminary experiments on the effect of changes in the ionic composition of the perfusing medium show that Ca-ions may have a specific effect on these processes. The values above refer to a concentration of 0.3 mM Ca^{++} . However, if this concentration is increased to 0.9–1.2 mM, an increase of the order 30–50% is observed in the rate constants k_1 , $k_3 (= k_{30} + \bar{k}_4)$, and \bar{k}_4 , and the constant k_2 is roughly doubled. The use of Ca-free solutions (0.3 mM EDTA) did not bring about further changes in the values that apply for 0.3 mM Ca^{++} . This dependence on the Ca-concentration in the external medium is, however, only

observed when the bleaches are small. With large bleaches the average rate constants of the decay reactions appear to be independent of the amount of Ca^{++} present and unaffected by the elimination of these ions.

These findings are interesting from a physiological point of view for two reasons: 1. In the living rod it has been assumed that Ca^{++} ions are liberated from the rod discs when illuminated. These ions would then act on the external membrane of the outer segment and thus mediate excitation by reducing its Na-permeability and thus the inward flow of dark current (Yoshikami & Hagins (1973), see also Brown & Pinto (1974)). 2. In the excised and opened frog eye as well as in the eye of the crucian carp it appears that rod dark adaptation after small bleaches follows the same time course (thresholds on a log scale) as the decay of the photoproduct bound retinal (and MIII) (Donner & Reuter 1968, Donner 1973), the decay of which appears affected by Ca^{++} . This relationship suggests that there is a causal link between rod sensitivity and the amount of these substances present.

A direct demonstration of the release of Ca^{++} from disc membranes of rod outer segments as a consequence of rhodopsin bleaching, as well as of active accumulation of Ca^{++} in the dark and light, has been given by Mason et al. (1974) (see also reference to the work of Szuts in Poo & Cone (1974)). The present results suggest that the decay processes after the MII stage are partly dependent on a sufficiently high concentration of external Ca^{++} and proceed with a slower rate when this concentration is low. Presumably, the internal Ca^{++} -concentration (10^{-7} – 10^{-8} M in the extradiscal space assumed by Yoshikami & Hagins 1973) rises when the external concentration is increased.

The dependence on the Ca^{++} concentration could be explained if Ca^{++} acted as a catalyst in the decay reactions. Or it may mean that Ca^{++} is actually bound in some of these reactions. If Ca-binding could be associated with the decay of bound retinal and MIII it might give a clue to the mechanism of action of these substances in regulating rod sensitivity. After large bleaches the extradiscal Ca^{++} -concentration may in either case

be insufficient to participate in the reactions, even with higher concentrations of Ca⁺⁺ outside the cell. Thus the effect of Ca⁺⁺ on the rate constants would become negligible under these conditions, as actually observed in our measurements.

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